

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

BOTANIK TERMINLI ELEKTRON LUG'ATLARNING MIKRO VA MAKRO TUZILISHI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada botanik terminlarni o'z ichiga olgan elektron lug'atlarning mikro va makro tuzilishi tahlil qilinadi. Botanik terminli elektron lug'atlarining mikro tuzilish qismi terminlarning morfologik, semantik va grammatik xususiyatlarini qamrab olsa, makro tuzilish qismida esa lug'atning umumiy tuzilmasi, qidiruv tizimlari va foydalanuvchi interfeysi haqida so'z yuritiladi. Maqolada xalqaro va milliy elektron lug'atlar tahlil qilinib, ularning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari haqida mushohada qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: botanik terminlar, elektron lug'atlar, mikro tuzilish, makro tuzilish, leksikografiya.

Hozirda biz yashayotgan fan va texnologiyalar asrida elektron lug'atlar zamonaviy leksikografiyaning ajralmas qismi bo'lib, ayniqsa, ilmiy sohalarda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Botanika sohasidagi terminlar ko'p qirrali va murakkab bo'lib, ularning aniq va tushunarli tarzda taqdim etilishi dolzarb masalalardan biridir (Hartmann, James, 1998). Elektron lug'atlarning ichki tuzilishi mikro va makro qismlarga ajratiladi. Mikro tuzilish - alohida leksik birliklarning ichki tuzilishi va tavsifi bilan bog'liq bo'lsa, makro tuzilish - lug'atning umumiy tuzilmasini, tartibini va qidiruv imkoniyatlarini o'z ichiga oladi (Bergenholtz, Tarp, 2010). Ushbu mavzuni o'rganish jarayonida taqqoslash va tahlil metodlaridan foydalangan holda, English Oxford Living Dictionaries (OUP, 2020) va O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati (O'zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2008) asosida botanik terminlar qiyoslandi. Mikro va makro tuzilish elementlari Lej'er (2003) tomonidan belgilangan lug'at tuzilishi mezonlari asosida tahlil qilindi, yani odatda elektron lug'atlardagi mikro tuzilish odatda quyidagi elementlar: terminning talaffuzi, grammatik ko'rsatkichlari, morfologik tuzilishi, sinonimlari va o'simlikning ilmiy nomlanishi va boshqa bir qancha tarkibdan iborat (Atkins, Rundell, 2008). Masalan, *rose* termini "English Oxford Living Dictionaries" da *atirgul* sifatida ilmiy nomi bilan beriladi, o'zbek lug'atlarida esa bu jihatlar ba'zan yetarlicha yoritilmaydi (Qosimova, 2019). Yana bir misol sifatida quyida apple (olma) botanic terminining elektron lug'atning mikro tuzilishi qoidalariga asosan berilishini ingliz va o'zbek tillarida ko'rib chiqsak:

Inglizcha:

apple

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Linguistic information:

Gram.inf.: noun (n)

Pronunciation:

Transcription: /'æpəl/

Etymology: Old English æppel apple; any kind of fruit; fruit in general, from Proto-Germanic ap(a)laz (source also of Old Saxon, Old Frisian, Dutch appel, Old Norse eple, Old High German apful, German Apfel), from PIE ab(e)l- “apple” (source also of Gaulish avallo “fruit” Old Irish ubull, Lithuanian obuolys, Old Church Slavonic jabloko “apple”), but the exact relation and original sense of these is uncertain.

Common names: -

Phrases and phraseological units: as **American as apple pie** – it means that something has qualities, or features, that are typical of the United States or the people of the United States. Example: My brother drives a Ford truck and wears blue jeans every day; he is *as American as apple pie*. **an apple a day keeps the doctor away** – Apples are considered a nutritious food; so this expression is intended as advice. To stay healthy (and to not have to visit the doctor) you should eat healthy food like, an apple, every day. Example: Whenever I get sick my mother always reminds me to take care of myself by saying, “*An apple a day keeps the doctor away.*” **the apple of my eye** – This is a way of referring to a favorite, or beloved, person. Example: My daughter is **the apple of my eye**; she makes me happy every day. **(like) comparing apples and oranges** – This expression is used when someone is talking about two non-similar items, but trying to compare them as though they were similar. Example: You can't compare who works harder, me or you; I am a teacher and you are a fisherman, and that is like comparing apples and oranges. **one rotten apple spoils the whole barrel** – This expression means that one bad person influences everyone around him or her and can make them act bad too. Example: Jimmy is *the rotten apple that spoils the barrel* in my class, I wish I didn't have to be his teacher all year. **How about them apples? Or How do you like them apples?** This question is the same as ‘What do you think of that?’ Asking this question is usually a way of bragging or showing off. Example: I was picked to join the basketball team and you weren't. *How do you like them apples?*

Botanical inform:

Botanical name: *Malus domestica*

Family: Rosaceae

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mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

Definition: the fleshy, usually rounded red, yellow, or green edible [pome](#) fruit of a usually cultivated tree (genus *Malus*) of the rose family

Common species: red delicious, gala, granny smith, golden delicious, lady, baldwin, mcintosh, honey crisp, fuji and cortland.

Bloom time: depends on climate of the local climate

Native area: Central Asia

Climate: changeable because of species

Medicinal use: it improves digestion, prevents stomach disorders, gallstones, constipation and liver disorders. Furthermore, apple helps to treat rheumatism, dysentery, eye disorders, a variety of cancer and gout. It can even prevent the onset of some chronic diseases like Parkinson's and Alzheimer's.

For extra information: <https://www.etymonline.com/word/apple>

O'zbekcha:

olma

Lingvistik ma'lumot:

Grammatik: ot

Etimologiya: Qadimgi turkiy tildagi ol- "olmoq" fe'lidan *-ma* qo'shimchasi bilan tuzilgan so'z. Qadimgi manbalarda *olmila* shakli ham bor. *Olmila* so'zining etimologiyasi aniq emas.

Sinonim: alma

So'z birikmalari va frazeologik birliklar: - *olmaning tagiga olma tushadi* – Axir olmaning tagiga olma tushadi – ku! Movlono Jaloliddin Rumi (masnaviy). *olmadek qizarmoq* - Adolat butunlay o'zgarib ketganga o'xshaydi, yuzi oydek to'lib, naqsh **olmadek qizarib** turibdi. *ko'zi olma termog* – Bo'ri polvon atrofga alanglagancha ko'zi olma terdi;

Botanik ma'lumotlar:

Botanik nomi: *Malus domestica*

Oila: ra'noguldoshlar

Ta'rif: ra'noguldoshlar oilasiga mansub daraxtning (*Malus* turkumi) go'shtdor, yumaloq, qizil, sariq yoki yashil ranli mevalari iste'mol qilinadigan turi

Turi: afrosiyob, borovinka tashkentskaya, go'zal, oydin, feruza, saratoniy, rozmarin

Gullash vaqti: mahalliy iqlimga bog'liq

O'sadigan joyi: Markaziy Osiyo

Iqlimi: turlari tufayli o'zgaruvchan

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Dorivor xususiyati: ovqat hazm qilishni yaxshilaydi, oshqozon, o't toshlari, ich qotishi va jigar kasalliklarining oldini oladi. Bundan tashqari, olma revmatizm, dizenteriya, ko'z kasalliklari, turli xil saraton va podagra kasalliklarini davolashga yordam beradi. Bu hatto Parkinson va Alsgeymer kabi ba'zi surunkali kasalliklarning boshlanishini oldini olishi mumkin.

Qo'shimcha ma'lumot: <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Olma>

Makro tuzilish jihatidan esa ingliz tilidagi lug'atlar qidiruv tizimlari, havolalar va ko'p qirrali qidiruv imkoniyatlari bilan ajralib turadi. O'zbek elektron lug'atlari esa bunday funkcionallik jihatidan cheklangan (Shodmonov, 2021). Shu sababli, o'zbek tilidagi botanik lug'atlarni rivojlantirishda xalqaro tajribadan foydalanish muhim (Bergenholtz & Tarp, 2010).

Botanik terminli elektron lug'atlarning samaradorligi ularning mikro va makro tuzilishiga bog'liq. Mikro tuzilishda aniq va to'liq lingvistik tavsif berilishi, makro tuzilishda esa qulay qidiruv va navigatsiya tizimlari mavjud bo'lishi zarur (Tarp, 2009). O'zbek tilidagi elektron lug'atlarning rivojlanishi uchun xalqaro tajriba va zamonaviy texnologiyalarni jalb qilish muhimdir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Atkins B.T., Rundell M. (2008). The Oxford Guide to Practical Lexicography. Oxford University Press.
2. Bergenholtz H., Tarp S. (2010). Leksikografiyaning nazariy asoslari. Aarhus Universiteti Nashriyoti.
3. Hartmann R.R.K., James G. (1998). Dictionary of Lexicography. Routledge.
4. OUP. (2020). English Oxford Living Dictionaries.
5. O'zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi. (2008). O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati.
6. Qosimova N. (2019). O'zbek leksikografiyasida botanik terminlarning o'ri. Filologiya masalalari jurnali.
7. Shodmonov A. (2021). Elektron lug'atlarda terminologik muammolar. O'zbek tilshunosligi.
8. Tarp S. (2009). Leksikografiya nazariyasi va amaliyoti. Walter de Gruyter.